

THE PROBLEM OF NATIONAL PERSONNEL TRAINING IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM OF THE UZBEKISTAN SSR

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Abstract: In the article, the place and role of the education system in the training of national personnel in the Uzbek SSR from the years of reconstruction of the national economy after the Second World War to the 80s of the 20th century, the changes that have occurred in this regard, the laws and decisions issued by the Soviet authorities in the field of training of specialists, qualified personnel in various fields efforts were made to highlight the progress achieved in providing and the problems that have arisen and the state of inclusion of representatives of the local nationality on the basis of available sources.

Key words: field of education, special secondary education, vocational schools, technical school, communist party, politics, communist ideology, working class, workers, decisions, law.

INTRODUCTION. During the period of Soviet colonialism in Uzbekistan, the need for quality personnel in the economic and social spheres was not studied scientifically. As a result, serious mistakes were made in the planning of personnel training in the republic, more personnel were trained in some areas than necessary, and in some areas, especially in the sectors dealing with technical development, there was a shortage of workers from representatives of the local nationality. In the years after the Second World War, the laws and decisions regarding the education system were considered to be the main issue of training young people for the profession, preparing them as specialists needed for the national economy and other fields.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT. Many monographs, brochures, articles, collections of documents and memorial books have been published on the education system in Uzbekistan and its condition from the years after the Second World War to the 1980s. Scientific researches on the topic created during the Soviet period were created more in accordance with the communist ideology, in which the advantages of the Soviet-era education system, the reforms implemented by the communist party in the field of education, their results, positive evaluation of the changes in the field of training of pedagogues, together with the vocational training of local youth moved to problems .

Discussion. On December 24, 1958, the Law "On Strengthening the Connection of School with Life and Further Development of the Public Education System" was adopted. In accordance with the law, secondary general education schools were transformed into 11-year secondary general education schools in the direction of production. The goal was that within three years, high school students should acquire a profession, get a secondary-special education and serve as laborers in various fields of the national economy. Some results have been achieved regarding the implementation of this law. During 1958-1961, there were 991 schools in the republic where industrial education was introduced under industrial enterprises, collective farms and other organizations [1.27].

After the Second World War, a number of reforms were implemented in the system of secondary special and higher education in the preparation of specialist personnel for various sectors of the national economy. However, the difficult economic situation at that time did not allow young people of the local population to study in educational institutions, and prevented them from training highly qualified specialists. In particular, in 1950-1953, Uzbeks made up 30 percent of the students who graduated from higher educational institutions, and 33 percent of those who graduated from secondary specialized educational institutions [2.89].

Due to the unjustified involvement of Uzbek youth in public and political activities and agricultural work in high schools, they would not have the opportunity to obtain the knowledge required to enter higher education institutions. Also, one of the main reasons was the introduction of a foreign language in the exam for admission to higher educational institutions and Russian language classes for young students. As a result, the decrease in the number of young people of local nationality in higher education institutions of the republic affected the decrease in the weight of national personnel. Especially in rural areas, this led to a lack of specialist personnel.

In connection with the establishment of a full secondary education system in the Uzbek SSR in the 50s and 60s, in which education was linked to production, the Ministry of Education of the Republic, the heads of public economic councils of Gosplan, enterprises, construction, state farms and kolkhozes are responsible for the planned and organized employment of young people who have completed school. great responsibility was given. During the years 1959-1965, a special technical educational institution for training highly qualified workers with secondary education was built and put into operation in

25 places of the Department of Labor Reserves. 32,000 students who graduated from the eight-year school are admitted to technical schools[3.101].

In 1946-1958, qualified personnel for Uzbekistan's industry were trained through vocational and technical education networks and directly in production itself as a brigade and by individual training. Vocational and technical schools and educational institutions were rebuilt from 1954 and began to train qualified personnel for all sectors of the national economy in a centralized manner. Significant changes were made in the employment distribution of graduates and the use of their labor. A large number of students of state labor reserves, 16 thousand people were sent to work in agriculture, 11.6 thousand people in industry, 4.6 thousand people in construction, and 2.8 thousand people in transport and communication enterprises [4.227].

In the years after the war, the emergence of new sectors in the national economy of Uzbekistan required the formation of qualified personnel, while the introduction of new equipment and machine tools in industry, transport, construction, and agriculture put the task of training and retraining of engineering and technical personnel on the agenda. As a result, new forms of raising the scientific and technical level of personnel - advanced technical universities, experimental institutes, technical faculties of cultural universities began to appear [5.17]. However, many reasons such as the short period of study, the limitations of the programs, and their incompatibility with new technical means have led to unsatisfactory rates and scope of training.

Taking into account the need for technical knowledge in the field of production, training of workers and engineering-technical staff in production techniques was started in all large enterprises, and promotion of technical knowledge was intensified. Most of the heads of workshops, technicians, foremen and many advanced workers without special specializations enrolled in part-time and evening higher education institutions and technical schools. Young workers were attracted to the school of factory advanced production.

In the period under review, there was a problem of training qualified workers and engineering-technical staff from among the local population in this system. At the II meeting of the Central Committee of the KP (b) of Uzbekistan, this issue was considered as a task considered to be of primary importance in the republic [6.402]. As a result, by 1951-1955, the number of local engineers and technicians in production increased somewhat. During these years, 6,031 engineers graduated from Uzbekistan's technical universities, of which 1,162 were Uzbeks. Out of 10,227 graduates of industrial technical schools, 3,694 were

Uzbeks. In 1955, the total number of engineers in Uzbekistan was 10,190, while the number of technicians reached 14,240.[7,108] Also, several employees from Uzbekistan were sent to major enterprises in the center for training. For example, in 1950, Uzbek workers were sent to several enterprises on the banks of the Urals and the Volga [7.108].

During the Soviet Union, the issue of personnel training was considered a major economic and social problem due to the surplus of labor resources in Uzbekistan compared to other countries in Central Asia. Therefore, the number of workers and servants in the republic increased year by year. In 1958, their number increased by 500 thousand compared to 1940. By 1965, it increased to 400,000. It was 1 million 600 people [3.108].

Despite the considerable increase in the number of workers in the population, our republic was in 13th place among the Soviet republics according to this indicator, according to the data of 1979. It should also be recognized that Uzbekistan was lagging behind in terms of the weight of the national cadres of the workers. In the following years, a number of serious measures were taken and appropriate decisions were taken on ways to rationally solve this problem . Despite the positive changes achieved at the moment, the distribution of national personnel in some sectors was extremely uneven, and this situation could not be considered satisfactory.

RESULTS. There were many shortcomings in the number and quality of personnel in Uzbekistan. Despite the lack of labor resources, qualified personnel. in the republic, especially in the newly assimilated regions, it was clearly not enough. For example, in the Agriculture sector alone, there was a significant disparity between the number of employees capable of equipping farms with machinery and managing it. In particular, by the beginning of 1971, there was a shortage of more than 40,000 tractor drivers and many other mechanics in the republic, due to the low ratio of shifts and insufficient use of equipment. The available personnel is unevenly distributed among the regions and districts of the Uzbek SSR. The scale and profile of new personnel training in vocational schools, higher and secondary special educational institutions did not correspond to the real needs of cotton farming, cattle breeding and other branches of agriculture. The share of female mechanics was low.

In order to eliminate these shortcomings, great work was done on the implementation of the personnel policy in the republic based on the decisions of the government. That is, first of all, a unique system was created for the training

of managers, as well as specialists, public workers, and modern professionals. However, in ensuring the precise coordination of the developed plans for the training of specialist personnel and improving their qualifications with the plans for the production of new equipment and its supply to the republic's farms, it is necessary to combine vocational guidance in general education schools, taking into account the zonal characteristics of the composition of agricultural production and its specialization. and in the development of scientific-methodological developments in order to increase their efficiency, there were enough shortcomings in the issue of expanding the training of pedagogues for the purposes of production pedagogy faculties under republican pedagogical higher educational institutions for rural vocational schools.

CONCLUSION. During the studied period, as a result of the reforms implemented in the system of training qualified specialists in the Uzbek SSR, a large number of workers were trained in various educational institutions and worked in various sectors of the economy in the republic. Although a number of positive changes have been achieved in this area, due to difficulties in the socio-economic sphere of this period, in the issue of national personnel training, it was not possible to study the representatives of the local nationality in educational institutions, and it prevented the work of training highly qualified specialists from them. Uzbeks made up a small number of graduates of higher educational institutions and secondary specialized educational institutions. At the same time, personnel trained in educational institutions were trained on the basis of communist ideology. However, many workers in various fields who are devoted to their profession have always contributed to the reconstruction and development of the national economy of the republic through their work.

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